

THE OPINION OF WESTERN SCIENTISTS ON THE FORMATION OF MUSICAL AND RHYTHMIC COMPETENCE IN FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS

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Abstract: in this article, the views of Western thinkers on the formation of musical and rhythmic competences, the proximity of music to the moral world of a person, music in pedagogy, the spirit in the synthesis of plastic arts, the great possibilities of educating the body, combining poetry, dance, philosophy, creativity, etc. written about.

Key words: music, rhythmicity, competence, Western thinkers, morality, pedagogue, art, spirit, education, poetry, dance, philosophy, creativity.

Introduction.

The great Greek philosopher and scientist Aristotle (384-322 BC) made a great contribution to the development of the musical aesthetics of classical Ancient Greece. Unlike Plato, Plato's student and Alexander the Great's teacher in 343 BC, Aristotle took a realist position, trying to show that music was entirely of earthly origin and related to the diverse realms of human emotion. Aristotle considered poetry and music to be the highest form of art.

The main part. Music has special qualities because, according to Aristotle, it is capable of directly expressing moral virtues. "*Rhythm and melody*," says Aristotle, "contain anger and gentleness, courage and temperance, and all their opposites, as well as other moral virtues which come closest to the truth." The closeness of music to the moral world of a person, according to Aristotle, is explained by the fact that music can directly convey the movement and energy underlying the moral actions of the soul. "*Why*," asks Aristotle, "*only what is heard through sensory perception has a moral character*." After all, without words, the tone has a moral character, but it has no color, no smell, and no taste. But only because it involves action. These actions are active, and actions are signs of moral characteristics [1, p. 45].

In practice, the rhythmic part of the method involves indicating time with hand movements, including tempo and beat, and recording duration with other movements of the legs and body parts. For lesson and tempo, students walk, accent steps as needed, and contract arm muscles on metrically strong beats. As

students progress, they stop suddenly, stop emphasizing with one or both arms or one or both legs, substitute arm movements for leg movements, arm or leg movements with can put additional emphasis or perform other actions [3, p. 15].

For rhythms, individual movements are learned for specific times and then placed together in sequences that form a rhythm. Movements are first practiced individually, and then in groups. Students then learn to decode into movements a rhythm played by the teacher on the piano or drums, or a rhythm played by another student. The learning sequence is the same as that recommended by Gordon and Ferabend for auditory learning, but the learner verifies the physical movement from the sound. Ultimately, the student learns to keep the movement sharp or slow, to move forward or backward alternately, to move suddenly, to lie down or stand for a precise time, and all this requires a minimum of muscle effort and a continuous feeling of all for each. The student also learns to silently count time in accordance with the movements he is making, resulting in a heightened sense of movement.

Students learn to divide the stroke into different parts. The teacher calls out a number, and as the students move to the kick with their hands, they divide the kick into these divisions by taking that many steps for each kick. Independence between hands and feet is further developed until the student steps his hands on each note of the melody and moves to the opposite point. This is possible from a strict understanding of the beat and rhythm, which is understood as a movement and performed by the body in motion [6, p. 32]. Expressive gestures are added to show dynamics. In addition to rhythmic exercises, there is also music that forgoes formal movements to express rhythm, or instances where free movement is used to indicate what is expressed in musical form. Students can practice the actions to the sounds the teacher makes, or reverse the process and practice making sounds to the teacher's actions. Dalcroze was adamant that all of this training should take place before a child is given formal instruction on an instrument such as the piano. Without eurythmic training, playing becomes an intellectual exercise and the student cannot play expressively, because the whole body is not involved in the presentation of the music. They learn to divide the beat into different parts. The teacher calls out a number, and as the students move to the kick with their hands, they divide the kick into these divisions by taking that many steps for each kick. Independence between hands and feet is further developed until the student steps his hands on each note of the melody and moves to the opposite point. This is possible from a firm understanding of

beat and rhythm, understood as movement and performed with the body in motion. Expressive gestures are added to show dynamics. In addition to rhythm exercises, there are also cases where free movement is used to express things expressed in music or music that abandons formal movements to express rhythm [7, p. 20]. Students can practice the actions to the sounds the teacher makes, or reverse the process and practice making sounds to the teacher's actions. Jacques Dalcroze said that all of this training should be done before a child is given formal instruction on an instrument such as the piano. Without rhythm training, performance becomes an intellectual exercise and the student cannot perform expressively because the whole body is not involved in the presentation of the music.

In musical pedagogy, it has long been known that the synthesis of music and plastic arts has great possibilities for educating the soul and body. The idea that harmony is the basis of this beauty was known in Ancient Greece. According to Plato: *"It is difficult to imagine a better method of education than that which has been discovered and tested by the experience of centuries; it can be expressed in two ways: gymnastics for the body and music for the soul. Taking this into account, music education should be considered the most important thing [4, p. 7]. Rhythm and harmony penetrate deep into the soul, possess it, fill it with beauty and turn a person into a beautiful thought. He enjoys and admires beauty, perceives it with joy, is satisfied with it, and harmonizes his experience."* In ancient Greece, music for upbringing and education had a deeper meaning than it does today. And he combined not only harmony of sounds, but also poetry, dance, philosophy and creativity. It is these ideas that are important for education, and perhaps it is natural that teachers strive to educate children based on the *"laws of beauty"* and to make Plato's beautiful formula a reality. We pass from beautiful images to beauty. Thoughts are beautiful, from thoughts to a beautiful life and from a beautiful life to absolute beauty [2, p. 16].

Ancient Greek philosophers had many followers. Thus, the idea of the synthesis of music and movement was adopted by the Swiss musician and teacher Emile Jacques Dalcroze, based on which he developed a system of musical and rhythmic education of children at the beginning of the twentieth century. This system became known in many European countries and in Russia under the name *"artistic gymnastics method"*. The modernity and relevance of this technique is related not only to its name, it is widely used by many specialists of physical and music education.

Conclusion.

In the complex of rhythmic exercises, the Swiss teacher took music as a basis. Jacques Dalcroze's system was further developed in the works of his students and followers. They have done a great job of further developing practical materials for promoting the Jacques Dalcroze system in various schools. N.G. Alexandrova described rhythm as one of the means of biosocial education and placed it at the center of communication between pedagogy, psychophysiology, physical education, artistic development, etc. About the musical and rhythmic education of preschool children, N.A. Vetlugina says: *"children should be encouraged to perform creative tasks as soon as possible, create conditions for them to freely express their creative abilities, and encourage them to master rhythmic exercises more easily"* [5, 18 -p.]. In Koreneva's book *"In the world of musical dramaturgy"*, older children perform musical compositions in various rhythmic styles: folk, classical, modern, folkloric, historical and public compositions, among them [1, p. 18]. The etiquette, plasticity, gestures and elements of dance performance are formed in accordance with the period of creation of the musical piece.

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